

Table 3. Rankings of referral options if they were available for patients needing to see a psychologist (Ranked 1-10 with 1 being most preferable, reported as % of AHPs/clinicians providing that ranking, with the shaded number representing the most popular referral option at each ranking position)

Ranking of referral options	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 be able to see in a combined allergy HCP/psychology clinic (psychologist present)	52	18	13	11	4	2	1			
2 be able to see in a combined physician/psychology clinic (counsellor/ psychological therapist present)	14	43	12	20	5	5	1	1		
3 be able to refer to a separate psychologist clinic (but still part of allergy team)	30	14	44	7	3	2		1		
4 be able to refer to a separate counsellor/ psychological therapist (but still part of allergy team)	3	23	17	49	5	2	1	1		
5 be able to refer to a general hospital psychology service		2	7	5	54	21	8	4		
6 be able to refer to a general hospital counsellor/psychological therapist	1		1	5	9	51	22	8	3	
7 be able to confidently refer to local mental health services (CAMHS/CYPS or Adult teams)		1	3	2	12	8	53	17	4	2
8 be able to refer appropriate cases to hospital play therapist	1		3	2	7	7	12	50	5	13
9 be able to refer to third sector organisations for mental health support				1		2	2	11	72	14
10 flag to GP in clinic letter for further action through Primary Care					2	2	2	8	16	72